

“I have started this new trend at the end of [students’] notebooks”: A case study of a mathematics teacher caught within a reproductive cycle of hierarchical cascading of power

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Underpinned by the Human Condition Theory, this case study casts light on how an Egyptian mathematics teacher navigates his instructional approach with regards to problem solving while operating within a centralised governance model of national schooling. The study investigates multiple layers of contextual power dynamics affecting the teacher’s perspective and instructional approach towards mathematical problem solving. Data were collected in the form of teacher focus groups. Results indicate that the teacher held a view of problem solving that approximated the conventional view in the literature, but he felt compelled to adopt procedures-oriented methods in his daily practice. To combat this situation, he instituted a “new trend” outside of his main teaching practice: “at the end of [students’] notebooks.”

Introduction

The evolution of teaching and learning in modern Egypt can be considered as a product of colonial, post-colonial, monarchical, Marxist, liberal and extremist influences (Makramalla, 2020). In this study, we explore how, resulting from this evolution, socio-cultural power dynamics seem to exist that govern teachers’ classroom practices. In particular, we focus on one Egyptian teacher who participated in an activity-based extended teacher focus group. We explore how the aforementioned activity revealed this teacher’s perception of problem solving as a concept and how he viewed his role in teaching problem solving in his classroom, which we choose to view as situated in the context of a schooling microculture and a wider societal microculture. The study of micro and macro socio-cultural power dynamics, how they are historically and politically rooted and their influence on a teacher’s choice are globally relevant and there may be transnational similarities in that regard.

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Problem solving in the Egyptian teaching and learning context

To combat the post-colonial socio-cultural divide in view of knowledge dissemination and knowledge acquisition, the Egyptian government took the radical decision in 1967 to adopt a one-size-fits-all curricular dissemination and integration scheme that was to be executed across all national curriculum schools irrespective of their history, type (public or private) or socio-cultural contextual positioning (Ibrahim & Hozayin, 2006).

Sayed (2006) reports that, in the interest of safeguarding against extremist stimuli, the school mathematics governance model in Egypt was designed to be highly controlled by multiple layers of authority, which in turn all center around the Ministry of Education (MOE). Over the past 30 years, this centrally governed uniform teaching and learning model has been heavily memorisation-oriented (Sika, 2001), a matter that has recently been much debated by researchers, development agencies and policy makers (Ibrahim, 2010).

Recently, the MOE has launched its instructional and curricular reform initiative (EDU 2.0), an initiative that aimed to underpin the mathematics curriculum in problem solving oriented practices (Discovery Education, 2019). This radical shift in the underpinned curricular ethos was implemented in a tight timeframe, a matter that stirred public debate (Al-Ashkar, 2019). Teachers reported not grasping what the reform was substantially about and how they were to adopt it. The wider work, from which this case study is derived, aimed at exploring how teachers related to problem solving as a teaching and learning construct in an attempt to better understand how, building on this relatedness, a problem solving oriented curriculum might practically be enacted. This case study is hence situated in the transition period between the release of the EDU 2.0 initiative and its actual implementation.

Theoretical framework

This study is theoretically underpinned by Arendt's (1958) conceptualisation of the Human Condition Theory. In her work, Arendt (1958) situated individuals as operating within the 'vita activa', the active life as we are given. Within this framework, she distinguished between three states of activity of a human condition: the condition of labour, the condition of work and the condition of action (Figure 1).

As evident in Figure 1, the condition of labour designates the individual to operate within a system of reproduction, in order to ensure one's own sustaining within the system (*vita activa*). The condition of work shows a state where the individual becomes a creator, making artefacts that could challenge the 'vita activa' framework wherein the individual is situated; these are artefacts that outlive their maker and have the potential of shifting the actual reality where they are embedded. While these two modes of operation concern the individual, the third one relates to the interrelatedness between individuals in actions that could break through the actual reality. People work together to make progress and change the society where they operate in as 'actors'.

In light of the presented context of teaching and learning mathematics in Egypt, the case study at hand concerns an Egyptian mathematics teacher as an individual operating within a 'vita activa' which is characterised by a multi-layered, hierarchically cascaded, centrally governed power dynamic. As will be elaborated further below, our socio-political contextual

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analysis led us to situate the mathematics teacher within this system of centrality and uniformity as operating in the mode of the ‘labourer’.

Figure 1: Perspective on three states of activity

As this study is particularly focused on teacher relatedness to mathematical problem solving, an activity that is recognised to be important for students’ learning of mathematics at all levels of education in many countries internationally (e.g., Törner, Schoenfeld, & Reiss, 2007), we discuss also our conceptualisation of mathematical problem solving and respective tasks. According to Callejo and Vila (2008), a mathematical problem is defined as “a situation that proposes a mathematical question whose solution is not immediately accessible to the solver because he [or she] does not have an algorithm for relating the data with the unknown or a process that automatically relates the data with the conclusion” (p. 112). Building on this definition of a mathematical problem, we use the following definition of mathematical problem solving: “the activity that aims to generate a solution to a mathematical problem, that is, a response to the question in the problem that relates the data with the unknown” (Stylianides & Stylianides, 2014, p. 9).

The fact that a mathematical problem presents the solver with a situation for which there is no immediately obvious solution path implies that mathematical problem solving is ‘cognitively demanding’ (Henningsen & Stein, 1997) and cannot be reduced to memorisation or procedural forms of activity. We scoped our exploration of the teacher’s perception of mathematical problem solving and its classroom integration around mathematical problem solving tasks, which we conceptualised drawing on Stein et al.’s (2000) Mathematical Task Analysis Guide. As shown in Figure 2, the Mathematical Task Analysis Guide distinguishes between two broad kinds tasks: those with lower-level cognitive demands (‘memorisation’ and ‘procedures without connections’ tasks) and those with higher-level cognitive demands (‘procedures with connections’ and ‘doing mathematics’ tasks). Memorisation tasks are at the bottom of the classification in terms of their level of cognitive demands while doing mathematics tasks are at the top.

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the hierarchical ladder, the mono-system ensures that the same mathematics curriculum is practised in the same way across classroom contextual conditions. Being situated at the bottom of this hierarchical ladder, teachers are likely to feel trapped to reproduce this same culture of autocracy in their daily instruction (Figure 4). Naguib (2006) reported this course or action as being their only viable option, as implementing the prescribed form of instruction allows them to be socially and professionally recognised within a system that for many decades has fostered a societal expectation that reciting memorised knowledge is the main measure of success (Sika, 2001).

Figure 4: Situating the teacher as labourer within a reproductive culture

With this in mind, we view the Egyptian teacher as acting in the role of a ‘labourer’ (Arendt, 1958) within a culture of hierarchically reproduced forms of uniformity. Based on this choice of teacher positioning, teacher relatedness to problem solving classroom practices was explored, in order to address the following research question:

“How does an Egyptian mathematics teacher, who has been classified as operating in the position of a labourer within a system that for decades has been memorisation based, perceive mathematical problem solving tasks and the suitability of their integration in the local classroom?”

Research design

We present the individual case study (Yin, 2014) of one Egyptian mathematics teacher who operated in an Egyptian school governed by the wider centralised national agenda for schooling. Three mathematics teachers at this school participated, as part of a wider study, in a set of activities that were orchestrated in the setup of a focus group. The activities were

diversely designed to engage the teachers with a problem solving experience and reflection activities that related to the classroom implementation of problem solving tasks. The aim was to find out how teachers related to problem solving tasks with respect to the aforementioned classification of mathematical tasks (Stein et al., 2000), and how they related to their classroom implementation in light of their positioning within the wider power dynamic structure of centralisation.

The mathematics teacher whose case we present in this paper, Alan (pseudonym), has been teaching for the past 17 years at the same school, operating under a memorisation based national curriculum (pre-reform at the time of the study). Alan taught across all compulsory education year groups (years 1– 9). Despite being governed by the same contextual affordances and limitations as his colleagues were – such as lacking problem solving materials and having little autonomy and minimal classroom equipment – Alan stood out from his colleagues during the focus group as he expressed an interest in introducing his students to a different mathematical reality than the one in the pre-reform national curriculum (the national curriculum at the time of the study). We explore Alan’s perception of mathematical problem solving along with the contextual affordances and limitations that he grappled with.

One of the focus group activities was task sorting (Friedrichsen & Dana, 2003). Each teacher was provided with a set of mathematical tasks that we had pre-classified according to the Mathematical Task Analysis Guide (Stein et al., 2000). The teachers were unaware of the task pre-classification and were asked to single out the tasks that they would consider to be as mathematical problem solving tasks. A subsequent discussion uncovered teachers’ reasons for the chosen task classification. The teachers’ contributions allowed us to uncover their relatedness to problem solving tasks. In a second round of the same activity, the teachers were asked to single out the tasks that they would adopt in their daily practice. The teachers’ contributions in the subsequent discussion allowed us to better understand the micro-culture where the teachers were situated. It was important to uncover, based on the teachers’ selections and explanations, how the micro-culture of the school was influenced by the wider national macro-culture and how, in turn, the micro-culture was influencing the teachers.

We used the constant comparative method for data coding (Glaser, 1995) to identify a set of features that the teachers associated with mathematical problem solving tasks in the first round of the task sorting activity. The *perceived problem solving task features* were then mapped against the features in the Mathematical Task Analysis Guide to examine the extent to which the teachers’ perceived features of problem solving tasks aligned with those in the literature, notably Stein et al.’s (2000) ‘doing mathematics’ task category, which, as explained earlier, we (the researchers) associated with problem solving tasks. The data from the second round of the task sorting activity were also analysed from the perspective of the Mathematical Task Analysis Guide. Tasks that the teachers classified as well suited to the local context of their practice (the micro-culture of the school) were mapped back against the Mathematical Task Analysis Guide in an attempt to devise a code for reported *locally suitable task features*. *Locally suited task features* and *perceived problem solving task features* were finally contrasted against each other, in light of the literature guided framework (Stein et al., 2000).

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Findings

The wider study from which this work is derived presents an elaborate account of the task features that this particular teacher related to mathematical problem solving. For the purposes of this paper, we chose to focus on mapping the features that this teacher associated with mathematical problem solving against the Mathematical Task Analysis Guide. As indicated in Figure 5, this teacher perceived problem solving tasks as mainly being tasks that establish connections to and between mathematical concepts, a feature that according to Stein et al. (2000) rather related to ‘procedures with connection’ tasks (Figure 2). The teacher distinguished between the act of making a connection to real life and the act of making a connection between mathematical concepts, as indicated by the following excerpts:

“I think a mathematical problem solving task is a task where the student can make the connection between what he is learning and everyday life”.

“To me problem solving is when he can relate the mathematical concept, he [the student] is learning today with that, which he learnt in previous years”.

The focus seemed mostly on the act of connection making.

The teacher’s depiction of typical tasks utilised for daily instruction, however, were reportedly more procedural in nature (Figure 5). The teacher referred to a task that was “similar to something else the student was familiar with”, “required a known procedure to solve”, “has been solved before by the teacher”.

Figure 5: Mapping the main findings

The reflective part of the activity revealed that connection making mathematical tasks were the teacher’s preference when it comes to classroom mathematical tasks. Nevertheless, as illustrated in Figure 5, the teacher also expressed the view that, within the school micro-culture it, was more suitable to adopt procedures-oriented tasks. The teacher expressed a feeling of being “trapped” in the system to adopt procedures-based mathematical tasks in the daily instruction, despite him preferring to adopt connection-making tasks. The school micro-culture endorsed memorisation-based instruction and this culture could not be neglected within the hierarchical execution of a reformed curriculum. The teacher seemed to find a way to balance this dynamic. To overcome this “trap”, the teacher reported instituting a “new trend” in his daily practice: “I have started this new trend at the end of [students’] notebooks, where I write a problem that they can take home with them to think about. In the first five minutes of every session we have a conversation about what they have done with the problem. It’s the part of the lesson that they like most.”

Discussion

To discuss the teacher's so called "new trend", we build on our understanding of the contextual layers of macro-micro- power dynamics (Figure 3). Multiple layers of influence come into play affecting the teacher's own stance as well as classroom autonomy. In the following, we use the Human Condition Theory to untangle some of these layers.

The system expectation of the teacher

As indicated at the onset of this study, teachers operate as labourers within an organised and highly centralised system (Arendt, 1958; Naguib, 2006) where their value is determined by their ability to enact a replicated version of the national curriculum in their respective context of operation so as to prepare their students for a unified nationwide examination. In order to survive in this system, Alan has expressed the view of feeling "trapped". He feels obliged to adopt procedural mathematical tasks in line with the system's requirements. Alan, however, also reports a small window of opportunity to escape this trap. In the following, we analyse the findings by untangling the multiple vertical layers of this "trap", in an attempt to contextually situate Alan in this ecosystem of power dynamics.

The societal expectation of the teacher (macro)

As a result of operating in a memorisation-oriented teaching and learning culture, for multiple decades, over time societal expectations of schooling have been fixed around the act of certification (Hargreaves, 2006). As noted by Alan: "The parent does not send the child to school to learn. If they want their children to learn [skills] they can send them to summer camps. At the school, children should be prepared for the test." This in turn places additional demands on Alan to act (labour) in a way that sustains his existence within this system.

The school expectation of the teacher (micro)

Being immersed in a system and a society that places a high expectation on replicating the enactment of a memorisation-oriented mathematics experience in the classroom, in such a way that was nationally and societally accredited through certification, the wider study from which this work is derived addresses the role of the school as a micro-culture. It shows how the school, as a micro-culture of individuals working together, is positioned in such a way that it can either operate as an 'actor', presenting itself as a change agent to its stationed society (*vita active*), or as a 'labourer', yielding to the expectations of its stationed society in order to ensure its endurance (Figure 6).

In the first incident, the school acts as a change agent both within its micro-culture and to its stationed society. The former happens through fostering a local culture that appreciates problem solving thus counterbalancing the macro-culture, which appreciates memorisation, and producing local agents (teachers) that perceive mathematics accordingly. The latter happens through being stationed in its surrounding culture and operating with a dormant counter-culture that challenges the wider macro-culture. According to Alan, in response to the societal expectations of the context where the school is operating, the school is rather acting as a "certification institution". This adds a second layer of coercion on the teachers at

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the school to teach for the test, thus acting as labourers within a wider macro-system of procedures-based instruction.

Figure 6: Two modes of operation for a school

The positionality of the teacher

Resulting from the aforementioned three levels of positioning, a teacher operating within this cascaded hierarchy, as discussed in the onset of this work, would be classified as a ‘labourer’. Alan is indeed “trapped” to reproduce the same societally expected classroom experience. Yet, in accordance with his preference to teach connection-making mathematical tasks (Figure 5), he “instituted a new trend” that is reported to be the students’ favourite part of the lesson. Alan finds a window of opportunity to use the first five minutes of the lesson and the end of the student notebooks to introduce his students to his preferred type of mathematics tasks, namely connection making tasks. Alan reports taking the initiative to search for and find extra-curricular materials to use in the “back of notebook” section.

In this way, it can be argued that Alan – within his scope of operation – is shifting away from the afore-ascribed position of the ‘labourer’ (Arendt, 1958) towards the position of a ‘worker’, creating artefacts that challenge the status quo. By searching for tools and materials and by utilising a tight framework to *create* a learning experience that is different from the one prescribed in the national context (*vita activa*), Alan counterbalances the hurdle of access to mathematical tasks. He also opposes to the contextual limitations to transfer an image of mathematics that is procedural in nature and presents to his students a learning experience of mathematics that relates to the act of connection making. It can therefore be argued that, by instituting this “new trend”, Alan has placed himself in the position of a ‘worker’ (Figure 1).

Future research could involve conducting an in-depth interview with Alan in an attempt to understand what motivates him to counter-balance the system. The findings of this research could have implications for teacher professional development in high distance educational power systems, where teacher self motivation could be the only driving force to counter-balance a wider contextual dynamic. Tools and techniques could be set in place to empower a teacher, both with contextually suited materials to use and with an intrinsic drive to be a change agent.

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